

ETHICS IN MANAGEMENT AND ORGANIZATION DEVELOPMENT

Prof. L. Udayakumar* & Richard Samuel Edwin**

* Centre for Mahayana Buddhist Studies, Acharya Nagarjuna University, Nagarjuna Nagar, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh

** Research Scholar, Centre for Mahayana Buddhist Studies, Acharya Nagarjuna University, Nagarjuna Nagar, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh

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Abstract:

Helping your employees to recognize that they work in a multi-cultural environment or a global environment is an official reminder that there is an expectation that they will attend to cultural differences. Management and organization's extensive experience in workforce development can focus on this need. General awareness programs are a good start. In addition, Management and organization can provide specific programs targeted to functional needs global marketing, or global e-learning development, and/or on culture-specific needs, such as understanding you Chinese employees or presenting to Japanese audiences. The meaning of job titles and job responsibilities vary across cultures. Management and organization people can help you localize these - make them appropriate for various geographies in which these positions are located. ITAP has depth and breadth of experience in developing global employees. Cultures with a preference for certainty to know the structure/rules rather than handle ambiguity prefer competency based performance systems. Communicating exactly what is expected and defining the levels of behaviors and assessing employees all against the same criteria feels fairer to many employees. Performance systems that depend on manager's discretion can be viewed as "favoritism" and "unfair."

Key Words: Development, Ethics, Values, Company, People, System, Communication...etc.

Introduction:

As I have explained all the details of about professional ethics and values from introduction portion onward now I would focus only the management and organization development which will be the ending portion of this chapter.

1. Management and Organizational Development:

In today's business environment, with all of its challenges, we need employees who can be productive in a team environment, have good communication skills and can bring critical thinking and problem solving in to the job situation. To help you with these and other organizational developmental issues, Oklahoma's technology centers can deliver.⁴⁴We have this following tools and resources to address:

- Organizational needs, assessments and design
- Team skills training
- Supervisory training
- Human resource management
- Performance management
- Knowledge management
- Change management
- Organizational culture issues
- Employee retention
- Leadership development
- Pre-employment assessments
- Strategic planning

Often one of a company's most expensive assets is its human capital, the human resources of the organization. The management of your human resources focuses on recruitment and selection of employees who can succeed at their jobs and who will stay with your organisation, and making sure, those employees' abilities are optimally nurtured and developed so that the company can receive an optimal return on the investment made in these employees.

(a) Recruitment and Selection:

This is particularly challenging in a global organization where one of your biggest challenges will be finding, retaining and developing a superior global workforce. Management and people working in organisation know how to identify the "success factors"⁴⁵ of a position...which is a key to identification of professional candidates. Successful companies know what the jobs entail and seek to hire those expert professionals who can be more successful /effective with the lowest amount of support. Well written job descriptions, and competency models that clearly delineate success behaviors make for effective selection and hiring. Understanding cultural differences in the recruitment process, the selection of candidates and what motivates employees in various cultures is crucial to the success of global organizations.

(b) Targeted Interview Techniques:

In addition Management and organization people can support your selection process using and teaching you to use Behavior Event Interviewing (BEI) or Targeted Interview (TI) techniques. While not difficult to learn, they are far more effective at identifying exactly what capabilities particular candidates could bring to your organization. This is particularly important when recruiting and selecting across cultures.

(c) Assimilating New Employees:

In this competitive environment for attracting good global talent, companies need to pay particular attention to the perception of the company on the part of candidates and new hires. A well thought out and extensive assimilation process often makes new employees more likely to stay. This process should start before the offer is made, and many companies have assimilation plans for at least the initial six months on the job. This is especially important in group and relationship cultures as it helps the new employees feel welcomed into the group and gives them time and structure to establish relationships that will be important to the employee as well as anchor their loyalty to the company. Management and organization people can support your development of an effective on boarding or assimilation process.

(d) Developing Your Employees - Global Workforce Development:

Helping your employees to recognize that they work in a multi-cultural environment or a global environment is an official reminder that there is an expectation that they will attend to cultural differences. Management and organization's extensive experience in workforce development can focus on this need. General awareness programs are a good start. In addition, Management and organization can provide specific programs targeted to functional needs global marketing, or global e-learning development, and/or on culture-specific needs, such as understanding you Chinese employees or presenting to Japanese audiences.

(e) Localizing Your Employee Handbook and Job Descriptions:

The meaning of job titles and job responsibilities vary across cultures. Management and organization people can help you localize these - make them appropriate for various geographies in which these positions are located. ITAP has depth and breadth of experience in developing global employees.

(f) Performance Management:

Cultures with a preference for certainty to know the structure/rules rather than handle ambiguity prefer competency based performance systems. Communicating exactly what is expected and defining the levels of behaviors and assessing employees all against the same criteria feels fairer to many employees. Performance systems that depend on manager's discretion can be viewed as "favoritism" and "unfair."

(g) Global Leadership Selection and Retention:

If you know what it is that differentiates successful employees (their competency / behaviors) recruiting (external) and selecting (internal) against these competencies reduces the need for development (as you hire those who already have the needed skills) and benefits employees by recognizing those who already have the skills necessary to succeed.

(h) The Global Leadership Competencies Required for Success Include:

- The flexibility to work and manage across cultures
- The ability to be the voice of the local culture to home office while being the voice of home office to the local employees
- Understanding of and ability to adapt to cultural differences as they impact business practices. If you want your global leaders to succeed and stay, Management and organization people can help you:
- Define the behaviors associated with the actual success factors in your company
- Identify internal and external candidates who already have those success factors
- Provide accurate, reliable and detailed selection/recruitment data
- Provide detailed developmental reports
- Accurately assess and match role (job-demand) and individual (capability supply)
- Global Succession Management and Development:

Companies demand talent development / succession management to retain top talent and stay competitive. Linking both to a leadership competency model leverages investments, communicates expectations, and rewards (and retains) deserving talent. ITAP helps clients:

- Define Leadership and Management competencies
- Develop Succession processes
- Assess talent
- Identify areas for individual development

(i) Strategic Human Resources:

Unless your human resources professionals have a thorough knowledge of global business, what it takes to establish companies in new geographies and the needs of the local workers in country, you need the help that Management and organization people can give. We can be your local arm by temporarily outsourcing your start up HR in new geographies. Since a company's strategy will impact its employees, you need HR

support that understands the global landscape, everything from the recruitment and hiring techniques used in other countries, to the establishment of contracts, and compensation and benefits packages. Management and people of organization and strategic partners can support global companies in 200 countries around the world. Globalizing the HR Function: HR Staff Development:

- As companies globalise, their HR departments need to understand the challenges of working in and serving a global organization Management and organization can provide:
- Consultation for HR professionals to support them as they serve the needs of their global organizations
- Web content HR professionals can use to sell, to train or to explain how to be a better global business partner.
- Certification for HR professionals in the administration and use of Management and organization tools and services
- Act as temporary staff to supplement the capabilities of the existing professionals.

(j) Change Management:

The development of your organization and management may impact the change and success of the business. (Management's change and growth, across cultures and geographies requires the specific knowledge of the impact of change and growth needs in particular cultures). Management and organization need to understand the cultural nuances of change in many cultures and can support your organization in collecting and analyzing data on work culture. Our understanding of cross-border change initiatives can greatly reduce the usual issues created by change initiatives and address culturally specific issues relating to such cultural dimensions as need for certainty. Companies that institute either small or large scale change need to attend to the needs of the employees before, during and after this process. Management and organization people can support the change process throughout its life cycle. We can:

- Facilitate the charter of change implementation teams
- Provide consulting on employee communications
- Design and deliver cross-cultural training for multi-cultural or virtual implementation teams
- Provide support to team leaders with data/information from assessment results
- Provide the organization with data on the impact of the change.

E-strategy mapper creates a strategy map for business and helps organizations manage the strategy implementation through a strategic action plans. Organizations can benefit from the strategy mapper output to prioritize investments and their change initiatives, as well as putting figures to targets and preparing appropriate action plans. Imagine selecting "talent to watch" and assigning them an as yet unsolved business problem. Give them some parameters about expected outcomes, timeframes, and how to collect information - and watch them learn. One learning coach and monthly measuring their learning's insures they are:

- Learn about cross-functional issues
- Meet people from all over the company
- Get into" the day to day issues these people face.

Conclusion:

All aspects of organization development and management are linked in these resources. They access information about group facilitation, culture change, consulting, managing change, planned change, and leading edge topics such as emotional intelligence and large group processes. Check here for the best organization development and management resources. Values should be added in the management and organizational development. HR is the stabilizer and champion during organizational development. HR adds value by ensuring development efforts deliver lasting results. The question is how to do it? Use a principle-based approach to promote stability and manage your organization's embedded polarities. We need to build the organization on values."Our people are our most important asset."⁴⁶ One has heard these words many times, if he works in the human resources field. Yet how many organizations act as if they really believe these words? Not many. These words are the clear expression of a value, and values are visible through the actions people take, not their talk. Through our action values will live in organization. Values exist in every workplace. Your organization's culture is partially the outward demonstration of the values currently existing in your workplace. The question you need to ask is whether these existing values are creating the workplace you desire. We need to implement our values through the proper channel, such as for creating your organization's mission statement, vision statement. As the speed of change continues to increase, change management is a fundamental competency needed by managers, supervisors, human resources staff, and organization leaders. To tap your wisdom, my recent survey about change management afforded the opportunity to consolidate hundreds of years of experience in change management. Here, in your words, is your best advice about change management. It doesn't matter what kind of business you are in whether you are a multi-national corporation or a "mom and pop" business you will be affected by the economic development in China. China is like this huge vortex consuming both human and natural resources at an amazing rate, but the things that make us the most powerful

nation in the world are slipping. What development does take people who are willing to listen and help their colleagues. Development takes coaches, guides and advocates. Your culture is a result of the values, experiences, and behaviors shared by your employees. You can see your culture living in your language, symbols, stories, and work practices. Emphasize the values and culture you desire with motivational level.

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